

The Mediating Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior in the Relationship Between Organizational Communication and Job Performance

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Abstract

Keywords:

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This research aims to examine the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior, organizational communication and job performance and the intervening role of organizational citizenship behavior in this relationship. It is seen that organizational citizenship behavior strengthens communication within the organization by increasing cooperation among employees and positively affects organizational performance. However, despite the importance emphasized in the literature on this relationship, studies examining the mediating effect of sub-dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior on the relationship between organizational communication and job performance are limited. This study aims to make a modest contribution to the literature, highlighting the importance of effective corporate communication in organizations and emphasizing the idea of creating a culture that encourages organizational citizenship behavior in organizations by touching on the importance of going beyond the duties assigned to managers.

Örgütsel İletişim ile İş Performansı Arasındaki İlişkide Örgütsel Vatandaşlık Davranışının Aracı Rolü

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Örgütsel
Vatandaşlık
Davranışı,

Örgütsel İletişim,

İş Performansı

Bu araştırma, örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışı, örgütsel iletişim ve iş performansı arasındaki ilişkiyi ve bu ilişkide örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışının ara değişken rolünü incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışının çalışanlar arasındaki işbirliğini artırarak örgüt içindeki iletişimi güçlendirdiği ve örgütsel performansı olumlu yönde etkilediği görülmektedir. Ancak literatürde bu ilişkiye verilen önem vurgulanmasına rağmen örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışının alt boyutlarının örgütsel iletişim ile iş performansı arasındaki ilişkideki aracı etkisini inceleyen çalışmalar sınırlıdır. Bu çalışma ile literatüre mütevazı bir katkı sağlamak, örgütlerde etkili kurumsal iletişimin önemini vurgulamak ve yöneticilere verilen görevlerin ötesine geçmenin önemine değinerek örgütlerinde örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışını teşvik eden bir kültür oluşturulması fikrini vurgulamak amaçlanmaktadır.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's business world, the success of organizations is not solely contingent upon the performance of their employees. Organizational outcomes such as citizenship behaviors and communication also contribute to the success of organizations. Organizational communication is a critical factor that encompasses the flow of information, collaboration, and interaction within an organization. This communication network facilitates interactions among employees, their managers, and organization goals, thereby creating the organizational culture. On the other hand, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to the voluntary assumption of extra roles and responsibilities in the workplace, representing individuals going beyond their routine job duties to make additional efforts and contributions towards the workplace (Castro et al., 2004). These behaviors play a crucial role in shaping the organization's social capital and have significant effects on job performance.

OCB describes employees voluntarily engaging in non-work-related roles. These behaviors can include elements such as supporting the organization's goals and demonstrating commitment (Podsakoff et al., 2000). These behaviors strengthen communication within the organization by increasing collaboration, which has a positive impact on business performance (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2004). Therefore, OCB serves as a positive bridge between organizational communication and job performance. However, in the literature, the number of studies that examine the sub-dimensions of OCB as intermediate variables in the relationship between these two variables is limited. In this context, the purpose of this study is to understand how OCB acts as a mediating factor in the relationship between organizational communication and job performance and to develop effective citizenship behavior strategies to enhance organizational performance.

Clarifying the mediating role of OCB provides critical insights into how OCBs and practices can be improved. Furthermore, a detailed examination of the impact of OCBs on job performance can increase organizations' competitive advantage by enhancing employee motivation and strengthening internal collaboration. Therefore, understanding the topics addressed in this research, particularly the role of OCB's, will provide significant scientific contributions to academic circles, as well as leaders, managers, and researchers in the business world.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Organizational Communication

Organizational communication is defined as a set of social processes that ensure the execution of organizational activities in a purposeful and planned manner, the achievement of organizational goals in the best and most accurate way, and the constant updating of thoughts and information both within and outside the organization, as well as the presence of strong interactions within the organization (Aydm, 2019).

Organizational communication promotes the creation of a strong organizational culture, identity, and citizenship, as well as the establishment of strong professional relationships with all stakeholders (Goodman, 2000). In this context, there are three main functions of organizational communication: First, it aims to regulate and coordinate production activities, which require mutual and dynamic communication actions among all organizational members. Second, it seeks to socialize individuals to align them with organizational goals. Lastly, it aims to foster innovation to help organizations keep up with the rapidly changing world and respond to the evolving needs of individuals (Baker, 2007).

When considering organizational communication from a structural perspective, it can be divided into formal and informal communication. Tanrıverdi et al. (2010) define formal communication as "a type of communication conducted within an organization according to organizational rules, detached from the personalities of organizational members, and occurring between different statuses." Informal communication, on the other hand, occurs among individuals within the organization and relies less on rules and structures compared to formal communication, developing spontaneously (Jensen, 2003).

It is important that organizational members use the right tools in the process of achieving organizational goals and objectives. Organizational communication tools are classified into three groups: written communication tools, oral communication tools, and visual and auditory communication tools (Güllüoğlu, 2012). Written communication is defined as the transmission of feelings and thoughts in written form (Eyyüpoğlu, 2018). Oral communication can be defined as communication that occurs through spoken words, including factors such as conversation, listening, facial expressions, gestures, tone of voice, and emphasis. Visual communication is a form of communication that utilizes and perceives visual elements. Visual communication tools aim to engage

the individual more visually by actively using image and sound factors. Examples of visual communication tools include radio, television, videos, drawings, and exhibits (Sabuncuoğlu & Gümüş, 2016).

Effective organizational communication helps reduce uncertainty within the organization. A lack of communication leads to uncertainty within organizations, which can result in reduced organizational commitment, decreased productivity, insecurity, stress, job dissatisfaction, and ultimately, employee turnover (Ay et al., 2019). When organizational communication is either incomplete or absent, problems arise within the organization. A lack of communication leads to disconnection among individuals within the organization, impacting the organization's efficiency and resulting in issues such as a lack of trust, loss of motivation, and inefficiency (Oğuzhan, 2020).

2.2. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

OCB encompass actions such as helping colleagues resolve problems that arise during work, accepting instructions without causing issues, carrying out unexpected but mandatory tasks without complaint, assisting in keeping the work environment clean and organized, speaking positively about the job, organization, and managers to people and institutions outside the organization, creating a work climate with minimized conflicts and distractions, and conserving organizational resources (Organ, 1988). OCB refers to voluntary actions that are not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system but contribute to the effective functioning of the organization (Organ, 1988). Organ defined OCB as “individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization.” He emphasized that the discretionary nature of the behavior means it is not part of the job description, is not a job commitment for people, and is therefore entirely discretionary a matter of personal choice, and that not exhibiting the behavior does not result in any punishment (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Organ’s work, “Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Good Soldier Syndrome,” has been the most widely accepted study on OCB to date. In this work, Organ refers to OCB as the “good soldier” and examines it in five dimensions. These are altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and civic virtue (Organ, 1988).

- Altruism occurs when individuals consciously and voluntarily help their colleagues on a personal level. Examples of such behavior include guiding a new employee through orientation, assisting an employee with a heavy workload, providing an employee with needed supplies, etc. (Organ, 1990).
- Courtesy is the behavior of employees in informing other employees of the decisions they make about the organization and the results of their deliberations and practices (Organ, 1990). Organ (1988) illustrates courtesy behaviors as offering explanations and guidance to individuals who may be affected by organizational actions and considering the thoughts and suggestions of other employees in the use of organizational resources.
- Conscientiousness is individuals' voluntary contribution to the organizational process beyond their roles and responsibilities (Allison, Voss & Dryer, 2001). Conscientiousness refers to having a sense of duty and responsibility, which includes following rules by completing tasks on time, arriving at work on time, and making extra efforts to complete tasks if they are not completed on time (Organ, 1988).
- Sportsmanship in an organization defines how employees approach unpleasant situations, inevitable difficulties and inconveniences with tolerance and maturity, without whining or complaining (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Employees who demonstrate this behavior avoid expressing dissatisfaction with situations that do not align with their personal interests (Organ, 1990).
- Civic virtue is defined as the highest level of commitment to the organization, the tendency to participate in organizational life voluntarily and actively, and to contribute intellectually to organizational development. (Podsakoff, MacKenzie & Scott, 1994).

OCB can be defined as behaviors related to employees' roles or beyond their roles that are not part of the formal reward system (Naktiyok & İşcan, 2019). OCB also refers to a situation in which an employee goes beyond the tasks and responsibilities set by the organization and works more than expected (Sökmen et al., 2017). Examples of OCB include helping colleagues who have fallen behind in their work, providing information before actions that may affect other organizational members, gracefully tolerating minor inconveniences inherent in organizational work, and contributing appropriately to organizational management (Moideenkutty, 2005). It is known that OCB facilitates functioning, reduces conflicts, and increases efficiency through

organizational social mechanisms. Consequently, exhibiting organizational citizenship behavior can enhance organizational performance (Şehitoğlu & Zehir, 2010).

2.3. Job Performance

Job performance encompasses the tasks assigned to individuals in the workplace and the results they achieve over a certain period. Performance is not only a matter specific to individuals; it also involves management and other teams within the organization (Boz et al., 2021). Campbell emphasizes that job performance is a means to achieve specific goals within a job, role, or organization and is not the actions themselves. He highlights that job performance is not a single action but a “complex activity.” Performance is defined as observable, measurable behaviors that are relevant to the organization's goals (Campbell et al., 1990). In other words, job performance refers to measurable activities and results related to employees' contributions to organizational goals and objectives (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2017).

Job performance is divided into two categories: task performance and contextual performance (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993). Task performance can be defined as the total expected value of an individual's behaviors to produce organizational goods and services over a standard period (Motowidlo & Kell, 2012). According to Ramos-Villagrasa et al. (2019), task performance encompasses all behaviors aimed at producing goods and services within an organization. Contextual performance refers to behaviors performed in the social and psychological environment of the organization that contribute to organizational integrity (Ramos-Villagrasa et al., 2019). Contextual performance emerges as a result of personal performances (Kızıldaş, 2017). It is also known as extra-role performance (Özdevecioğlu & Kanıgür, 2009).

3. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Organizational communication is a fundamental element that significantly impacts job performance. Pincus (1986) demonstrated a positive relationship between organizational communication and job performance, while Kumar (2008) stated that certain dimensions of organizational communication show a meaningful and positive correlation with job performance. In a study comparing American and Taiwanese companies, Chen, Silverthorne, and Hung observed strong relationships between organizational communication and employee performance (Chen, 2018). Open, transparent, and effective communication channels increase employee motivation and promote collaboration and teamwork. Efforts to enhance employees' communication behaviors are expected to contribute to increased employee job satisfaction and performance (Giri & Kumar, 2010). In the other research, Ogunola & Akporaro (2015) found that internal communication within an organization has a meaningful relationship with job performance and increases efficiency and job performance.

A good communication pattern within an organization contributes to the strengthening and widespread prevalence of altruism and civic virtue, which are dimensions of OCB. Courtesy, a dimension of OCB, materializes as an opinion formed based on communication among the parties. In other words, the materialization of courtesy depends on the form of interpersonal communication, the content, the manner of reflecting intentions, and the style of presentation. The sportsmanship behavior, which is another dimension of OCB, refers to employees behaving more voluntarily in situations that require additional effort due to job requirements. Depending on the effectiveness of communication between managers and employees, sportsmanship behavior is expected to yield more meaningful results. A good relationship among all organizational employees is based on good communication (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2004).

Podsakoff and Mackenzie (1994) state that the presence of individuals with OCB for the organization makes the organization an interesting place to work and contributes to individual and group performance. From another perspective, OCB helps create a positive social environment in the workplace. In this environment, employees are happier and more motivated, which improves their job performance. (Bozer & Yanık, 2020). Numerous studies have demonstrated that OCB also has a positive and significant effect on job performance. Studies focusing on the general dimensions of OCB show that employees who exhibit this behavior are more committed to organizational goals than other employees, value teamwork, and are helpful, innovative, and creative individuals (Leana et al., 1983; Özdevecioğlu, 2003; Allen & Rush, 1998; Borman et al., 1995; Lowery and Krilowicz, 1994; Çelik & Çıra, 2013).

The positive impact of organizational communication on citizenship behaviors may allow for a reverse assessment in terms of willingness to communicate. Positive tendencies of employees toward OCB are likely to

increase the desire to communicate among employees. In this context, employees are expected to be more willing to fulfill citizenship behaviors and organize themselves toward organizational goals. This effort depends on the effective use of organizational communication. Employees' sensitivity to go beyond their roles within the organization to increase efficiency and productivity requires the presence of communication (Carmeli & Josman, 2006).

Based on these informations our research hypotheses as follow:

- H1: The altruism dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.
- H2: The conscientiousness dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.
- H3: The courtesy dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.
- H4: The civic virtue dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.
- H5: The sportsmanship dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Sampling and Measures

We adopted multi-item scales from prior studies to test our hypotheses. We used a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5). For the “organizational citizenship behaviour” scale, we used Bolat et al.’s (2009) scale. For the “organizational communication” scale, we used the employee-related dimension of the scale developed by Ballı et al. (2021). And finally, we used the in role job performance dimension of the “job performance” scale developed by Janssen et al. (2004).

Since the most developed industry in Turkey is in the Marmara Region, data was collected from this region. Data was collected through survey method and participants were determined on a voluntary basis. Participants were informed that there were no right or wrong answers to the questions and that all answers would remain anonymous.

There are 502 participants in our study. 253 (50.4%) of our participants were men and 249 (49.6%) were women. So, we can say that the number of men and women in the study is quite close. 219 (43.6%) of the participants are between the ages of 26-35, 131 (26.1%) are between the ages of 36-45 and 83 (16.5%) are between the ages of 18-25. According to this distribution, we can state that the participants are generally young people. Considering the education levels, 269 participants (53.6%) with bachelor’s degrees constitute the majority. Additionally, 96 participants (19.1%) have a master's degree and 76 participants (15.1%) have an associate degree. So, the majority of our participants have a high level of education. 279 (55.6%) of our participants are personnel, 97 (19.3%) are mid-level managers, 78 (15.5%) are low-level managers, 26 (5.2%) are senior managers and 22 (4.4%) are business partners.

4.2. Measure Validity and Reliability

After data collection, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed to assess the validity of the measures (as shown in Table 1). Items with factor loadings below 0.50 were excluded from the analysis. 1 item from OCBC, 1 item from OCBS and 1 item from JP were excluded from the analysis because their factor loadings were low. The final factor analysis performed is presented in Table 1.

CFI, NFI, TLI, IFI, RMSEA and χ^2/df were used to expound the fit of measurement model and data. According to Hair et al. (2010), CFI, TLI, NFI and IFI should be at least 0.90 for a good fit, and the maximal value for RMSEA should be 0.08 for an adequate model fit. In addition to this, according to Schumacker and Lomax (2004), χ^2/df should be between 1– 5 to the allowable. Our CFA outcomes indicated that the measurement model fits the data adequately ($\chi^2/df:2.931$, CFI:0.936, TLI:0.928, NFI:0.906, IFI:0.936, RMSEA:0.062).

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Reliability Results

Construct		Factor Loadings	AVE	CR	Cronbach's Alpha
OC	OC_1	0.756	0.679	0.967	0.966
	OC_2	0.836			
	OC_3	0.823			
	OC_4	0.863			
	OC_5	0.864			
	OC_6	0.865			
	OC_7	0.908			
	OC_8	0.849			
	OC_9	0.839			
	OC_10	0.839			
	OC_11	0.821			
	OC_12	0.844			
	OC_13	0.815			
	OC_14	0.567			
OCBA	OCBA_1	0.907	0.685	0.895	0.885
	OCBA_2	0.889			
	OCBA_3	0.595			
	OCBA_4	0.879			
OCBC	OCBC_2	0.772	0.660	0.853	0.846
	OCBC_3	0.910			
	OCBC_4	0.746			
OCBO	OCBO_1	0.904	0.750	0.923	0.917
	OCBO_2	0.836			
	OCBO_3	0.932			
	OCBO_4	0.784			
OCBS	OCBS_1	0.780	0.644	0.844	0.842
	OCBS_2	0.783			
	OCBS_3	0.843			
OCBI	OCBI_1	0.881	0.665	0.888	0.871
	OCBI_2	0.804			
	OCBI_3	0.754			
	OCBI_4	0.819			
JP	JP_1	0.848	0.685	0.897	0.908
	JP_2	0.853			
	JP_4	0.772			
	JP_5	0.836			

OC: Organizational Communication, OCBA: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Altruism, OCBC: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Conscientiousness, OCBO: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Courtesy, OCBS: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Sportsmanship, OCBI: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Civic Virtue, JP: Job Performance, AVE: Average Variance Extracted, CR: Composite Reliability

And so, average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) are evaluated in the direction of the recommendations of Fornell and Larcker (1981). Every computed value for AVE and CR exceeds the

recommended cut-off values, which are 0.50 and 0.70, respectively. In the direction of these upshots, convergent validity is supported. Cronbach's alpha are examined in order to assess the constructs' reliability. Nunnally (1978) states that Cronbach's alpha values have to be more than 0.70. In line with all these results obtained, it can be stated that the validity and reliability of the measurement are sufficient (as shown in Table 1). Before performing the hypothesis tests, correlation analysis was performed to determine the correlation coefficients between the variables. The obtained values are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficients

	OCBI	OC	OCBA	OCBC	OCBO	OCBS	JP
OCBI	1						
OC	0,589	1					
OCBA	0,700	0,567	1				
OCBC	0,669	0,513	0,764	1			
OCBO	0,680	0,506	0,792	0,913	1		
OCBS	0,665	0,554	0,661	0,678	0,729	1	
JP	0,713	0,537	0,753	0,893	0,868	0,692	1

OC: Organizational Communication, OCBA: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Altruism, OCBC: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Conscientiousness, OCBO: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Courtesy, OCBS: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Sportsmanship, OCBI: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Civic Virtue, JP: Job Performance

4.3. Hypotheses testing

Regression analysis was carried out to compute the path coefficients using Hayes' PROCESS (model 4) plug-in for SPSS. First, we calculated the direct relationship between the independent variable (organizational communication) and the dependent variable (job performance). According to the results obtained, organizational communication affects job performance ($\beta=0.3914$; $p<0.01$) in a statistically significant and positively. In the second stage, 5 mediator models were analyzed to see how each mediator variable affected the relationship between the independent and dependent variable (as shown in Table 3).

Table 3. Mediator Analysis

	Path	Effects		Path Significance		Model Significance	
		Direct Effect(β) (M \rightarrow Y)	Indirect Effect (β) (X \rightarrow Y)	LLCI (X \rightarrow Y)	ULCI (X \rightarrow Y)	R ²	F
Model1	OC \rightarrow OCBA \rightarrow JP	.4753**	.1694**	.1099	.2288	.4582	210.984
Model2	OC \rightarrow OCBC \rightarrow JP	.6423**	.1486**	.1002	.1970	.6065	384.600
Model3	OC \rightarrow OCBO \rightarrow JP	.6720**	.1133**	.0645	.1621	.6206	408.165
Model4	OC \rightarrow OCBI \rightarrow JP	.4397**	.1571**	.0954	.2188	.4457	200.601
Model5	OC \rightarrow OCBS \rightarrow JP	.3681**	.2123**	.1516	.2730	.4102	173.494

The direct effect of OC on JP is $\beta=0.3914$ ($p<0.01$).

X: Independent Variable, M: Mediating Variable, Y: Dependent Variable

** $p<0.01$

OC: Organizational Communication, OCBA: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Altruism, OCBC: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Conscientiousness, OCBO: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Courtesy, OCBS: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Sportsmanship, OCBI: Organizational Citizenship Behavior-Civic Virtue, JP: Job Performance

As shown in Table 3; 95% confidence intervals (5,000 bootstrap samples) for all indirect effects do not include zero. This demonstrates the importance of indirect impacts. First, when OCBA is included in the analysis

(Model-1), OC is still related to JP ($p < 0.01$), but the regression coefficient reduces from ($\beta = .3914$) to ($\beta = .1694$). Hence, these results revealed that OCBA partially mediates the relationship between OC and JP. So, **H1** was **supported**. Second, when OCBC is included in the analysis (Model-2), OC is still related to JP ($p < 0.01$), but the regression coefficient reduces from ($\beta = .3914$) to ($\beta = .1486$). So, these results showed that OCBC partially mediates the relationship between OC and JP. Hence, **H2** was **supported**. Third, when OCBO is included in the analysis (Model-3), OC is still related to JP ($p < 0.01$), but the regression coefficient reduces from ($\beta = .3914$) to ($\beta = .1133$). This means that OCBO partially mediates the relationship between OC and JP. So, **H3** was **supported**. Fourth, when OCBI is included in the analysis (Model-4), OC is still related to JP ($p < 0.01$), but the regression coefficient reduces from ($\beta = .3914$) to ($\beta = .1571$). Hence, these results indicated that OCBI partially mediates the relationship between OC and JP. So, **H4** was supported. Finally, when OCBS is included in the analysis (Model-5), OC is still related to JP ($p < 0.01$), but the regression coefficient reduces from ($\beta = .3914$) to ($\beta = .2123$). Thus, OCBS partially mediates the relationship between OC and JP. So, **H5** was **supported**.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Theoretical and Practical Implications

This research attempts to explain the relationships between Organizational Communication, Job Performance and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. According to the results obtained, a positive relationship between organizational communication and job performance was determined. Organizational communication positively affects organizational performance. Organizational communication positively affects employees job performance by increasing their motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Bakan ve Büyükbeşe, 2004).

It has been found that individuals who exhibit organizational citizenship behavior contribute to the creation of a social environment in organizations by increasing intra-organizational communication, and in this context, they contribute to making employees happier and more motivated, thus positively affecting their job performance. It is emphasized that organizational citizenship behavior plays a mediating role in the relationship between organizational communication and job performance. This research makes the following main contributions.

Our first hypothesis is “The altruism dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.” According to the results, H1 is supported. Good communication within the organization contributes to the strengthening of altruistic behavior (Somech and Drach-Zahavy, 2004). It has been observed that job performance is high in organizations where this behavior is prevalent and strong (Hidayah, 2018). Tsai et al. (2009) found that satisfaction with organizational communication increases the likelihood that employees in the organization will develop effective working relationships. In this context, organizational communication can be considered as one of the most crucial power centers in shaping and developing organizational citizenship behavior of employees in the organization.

Our second hypothesis is “The conscientiousness dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.” And, according to the results, H2 is supported. The healthy functioning of communication in the organization positively affects the organizational citizenship behavior of employees (Demirel, Seçkin & Özçınar, 2011). Since individuals with high conscientiousness behavior are motivated to fulfill their duties and responsibilities by making extra efforts (Organ, 1988), it has been observed that this situation positively affects their job performance.

Our third hypothesis is “The courtesy dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.” And, according to the results, H3 is supported. As a result of courtesy behavior, employees in the organization will be able to prevent potential problems that may occur in the work environment, warn each other about problems, and this will create positive interactions among employees. In this context, employees who exhibit courtesy behavior contribute to intra-organizational communication. This process will increase the feelings of gratitude among employees and strengthen the tendency to cooperate (Erok, 2018). Therefore, it will be observed that when courtesy oriented behavior is exhibited, job performance will increase.

Our fourth hypothesis is “The civic virtue dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.” And, according to the results, H4 is supported. Individuals with high levels of OCB tend to participate actively by establishing good communication within the organization (Podsakoff, MacKenzie & Scott, 1994). From another perspective, OCB helps to create a positive social

environment in the workplace. In this environment, employees are happier and more motivated, which increases their work performance. (Bozer and Yanik, 2020).

Our final hypothesis is “The sportsmanship dimension of OCB mediates the relationship between organizational communication and job performance.” According to the results, H5 is supported. Sportsmanship is when employees within an organization continue to perform at the highest level without complaining when faced with unexpected difficulties (Sharma & Jain, 2015). This behavior is nurtured by communication within the organization. The relationship between employees within the organization depends on good communication (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2004).

This study sheds light on the complex relationship between organizational communication, organizational citizenship behavior, and job performance by examining the mediating role of organizational citizenship behavior in this dynamic. Various recommendations can be outlined for managers based on this study:

Organizations can prioritize effective corporate communication. Managers should prioritize corporate communication in creating robust strategies that facilitate transparent information flow, encourage feedback mechanisms, and foster an environment where employees feel valued and heard.

In organizations, it is important to promote organizational citizenship behavior. Managers should actively support a culture that promotes OCB, emphasizing the importance of going beyond assigned tasks. Recognizing, acknowledging, and rewarding examples of Organizational Citizenship Behavior will reinforce these behaviors, enhancing a culture of mutual support and collaboration.

Investing in employee development can be recommended. Investing in training and development activities aimed at improving employees' communication skills and fostering a sense of ownership would be highly meaningful. Such activities enable employees to engage in meaningful interactions and effectively manage complex organizational dynamics.

Encouraging a culture of participation can be meaningful. Establishing platforms that encourage employee participation strengthens the sense of belonging and encourages proactive engagement. Managers should strive to create a culture where organizational citizenship behaviors develop organically through dialogue, collaboration, and idea exchange.

In summary, it is important for managers to recognize the intrinsic connection between corporate communication, organizational citizenship behaviors, and job performance. Prioritizing transparent communication, promoting a culture of mutual support, investing in employee development, and encouraging a culture of participation can help organizations unlock the full potential of their workforce and achieve sustainable growth and success.

5.2 Limitations and Future Research Directions

As with all research, this study also has some limitations and that may offer opportunities for further research. Data for this study were gathered from the Marmara region. This may limit the accuracy of the results. However, including companies from different regions in future studies can enhance the generalizability of this research. Furthermore, we didn't enforce any sector constraints while implementing this study. For this reason, it is suggested to conduct special studies with a more homogeneous participant population by using sector restrictions.

Only white-collar workers' data were gathered for this study. This represents another limitation for our research. Actually, OCB is an important factor for all workers. So, it is suggested to perform research on blue-collar workers.

In this study, the mediating role of OCB in the relationship between organizational communication and job performance was examined. Other researchers can investigate the mediator effect of other variables, such as organizational collaboration, job satisfaction and organizational justice.

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